

Reverting to old theories of ageing with new evidence for the role of somatic mutations

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Standfirst

With age, somatic mutations accumulate in the genome of healthy individuals, but the functional outcome of this increased mutational load has been unclear. Recent sequencing data support a functional role for somatic mutations in ageing and age-associated diseases.

Main text

More than 60 years ago, Szilard postulated that ageing could result from the accumulation of somatic mutations¹. This hypothesis is supported by premature ageing syndromes being predominantly caused by disruption of genes involved in DNA maintenance and repair. Somatic mutations undoubtedly accumulate in the genome of healthy individuals as they age and are recognized as a critical trigger for the expansion of malignant and non-malignant clones. However, whether increased mutation load causally contributes to the progressive loss of function observed in aged tissues is still a matter of debate.

Since next generation sequencing has been applied to normal cells, age-related accumulation of somatic mutations — single nucleotide variants (SNVs) and small insertions and deletions (indels) — has been observed in every tissue analysed². Collectively, data show that at advanced age every cell of the body carries thousands of SNVs, some of which are predicted to affect the protein sequence of a gene or its expression. These mutations are generally located on one allele. While estimating the impact of heterozygous variants is difficult, it is even more difficult to determine whether changes in multiple genes might exert a cumulative effect on cell fitness³. The complexity of this challenge increases when assessing tissues that contain millions of cells, each with its individual load and position of mutations. In addition, experimental systems that are generally used to address the question present a number of caveats, such as the impossibility to selectively and faithfully reproduce the amount, types and distribution of mutations naturally occurring with ageing, so that the complexity of the issue is further exacerbated by intrinsic weaknesses of available experimental methods³.

A fresh approach to the problem comes from evolutionary biology. If somatic mutations affect ageing, species with different lifespans should differ in somatic mutation rates. Accordingly, comparative genomic analyses amongst intestinal cells of the same type from 16 mammalian species have revealed that somatic mutations inversely correlate with lifespan (more mutations, shorter lifespan) and that mutation rate can explain 82% of the lifespan variability among analysed species⁴. Although this study is limited to a single cell type, it shows that somatic mutation is one of the strongest and most robust variables explaining why some mammals (humans being the longest-living in this sample set) live longer than others⁴.

While these data strongly argue in favour of a central role of genome maintenance in ageing, there is at least one major confounding factor that has to be taken into consideration. This is DNA damage, a signal inducing cellular responses that include apoptosis and senescence, ultimately impacting the occurrence of ageing phenotypes and lifespan⁵. As the DNA of each

cell is subjected to the daily attack of chemical stressors, living organisms have developed complex systems to maintain DNA integrity. Species in which DNA repair is less efficient and DNA synthesis and repair rely on error-prone mechanisms are expected to accumulate mutations faster, but also to accumulate uncorrected DNA damage, promoting cell death. In agreement, the inverse correlation between mutation rate and lifespan in different mammalian species has also been observed in cultured cells upon exposure to a chemical mutagen⁶. In this study, the shorter-lived species (mouse) accumulated more mutations, but also showed greatly enhanced proliferative defects after mutagen exposure compared to longer-living species⁶. Thus, inefficient genome maintenance has two consequences that can hardly be uncoupled: an increase in somatic mutations and a higher rate of DNA damage-induced cell cycle blockade and death.

The loss of chromosome Y constitutes an example of this complex cause–effect relationship. The frequency of this chromosomal alteration in circulating blood cells of male individuals correlates with lifespan and major pathologies. Since the Y chromosome contains few genes, none of which is known to exert explicit effects on cell survival, why would increased loss of this chromosome cause a reduction in lifespan? Analyses of large cohorts point to a common cause increasing both the rate of loss of chromosome Y and age-related phenotypes⁷. This common cause is germline genetic variation that weakens the mechanisms controlling genome maintenance and/or cell cycle check points. Interestingly, the loss of genes located on the Y chromosome also seems to contribute to the phenotype⁷. In the case of point mutations accumulating at random positions in the genome, it is still unclear whether the correlation between mutation burden and lifespan reflects inefficient genome maintenance or rather is due to the downstream consequences of mutations (alterations of important genes).

More focused approaches can perhaps be used to explore whether alterations of genes subject to somatic mutations can contribute to well-defined diseases associated with ageing. A recent study shows that neurons of patients with Alzheimer disease (AD) accumulate more mutations than those of healthy individuals⁸. The increased mutation rate is due to enhanced nucleotide oxidation and yields a recognizable mutational pattern. The authors estimate that the excess of mutations in AD neurons increases the chances of biallelic inactivation of a functional gene in a recognizable fraction of neurons. Mutated neurons are likely to contribute to cognitive impairment and disease progression, thus pointing to a functional role of somatic mutations in this specific age-related disease⁸.

An advantage of this study is the analysis of single genomes and well-defined neuronal populations. This strategy has allowed identification of the excess of mutations in a specific subset of neurons present in the prefrontal cortex, whereas this excess was not apparent when sorted neurons were analysed in bulk⁹. Single-cell whole-genome sequencing (scWGS), however, has a potential weakness, as mutations detected with this technology have been shown to contain artifacts⁹. Technical advances have improved scWGS, but, being demanding and costly, it is usually performed on a fairly low number of cells. In fact, cell numbers in scWGS studies are very far from the current standards for single-cell RNA sequencing studies. This limits the depth of analysis at the cellular level. By contrast, scWGS is one of the few techniques able to overcome a challenge that has characterized analysis of somatic mutations in normal tissues. Given that every cell acquires distinct variants during life, mutated alleles are very rare and almost impossible to detect with regular bulk sequencing. Instead, somatic variants can be readily identified in clonal populations that either naturally grow in vivo (such as tumours or clonal structures) or are artificially expanded in vitro. The predominance of studies based on clones produces a bias in currently available data, which are enriched for mutations detected in highly proliferating cells.

Proliferating cells are not entirely representative of a tissue. Therefore, an unbiased analysis of all cellular components is necessary before we can draw conclusions about somatic mutations and organismal ageing. Technical improvements to bulk genome sequencing

include methods based on detection of variants found on both strands of the same DNA molecule. One such method has allowed detection of mutations in non-proliferating cells and has shown unprecedented accuracy⁹. But, as observed for the brain of patients with AD, bulk analyses may overlook rare subpopulations that, in some cases, could be the real drivers of disease and ageing. For example, in the kidney, analysis of selected cells that are able to grow in vitro has been used to enrich for specific cellular populations that are otherwise rare in the tissue and difficult to study. This analysis found a cell subset that is prone to mutations and more likely to play an important role in kidney tumorigenesis and possibly ageing¹⁰. Thus, while an exhaustive characterization of ageing tissues via scWGS is still out of reach, a combination of sequencing methods may be used.

Our understanding of the accumulation of somatic mutations in normal tissues with ageing is still superficial, but evolving technology promises to improve our characterization of different tissues and cell types. At present, both the inverse correlation of mutations with lifespan in different species and the excess of potentially harmful mutations in AD neurons argue for an active role of somatic mutations in the ageing process.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.